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READING THROUGH APPROPRIATED AND POLITICIZED
CONSTRUCTION OF HISTORICAL MEMORY IN MANIPUR WITH
SPECIAL REFERENCE TO HIJAM IRAWAT'S POLITICAL TRAJECTORY: A
CONFRONTATIONIST INTERVENTION

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Abstract: *A disregard for simple historical fact-checking and contextualizing can damage much more than the temporary and short-sighted gains extracted from a vested and gullible appropriation of historical narratives and their key protagonists. Also, the ethical issue involved needs to be hammered into the understanding of necessity (based on emotionality/sentimentality/vested political ends) vs longevity (based on unadulterated study of recorded facts) while constructing narratives. Also, the psychology of fundamentalism and extremism, especially of the religio-nationalistic sort, has parallels in the local revivalist as well as the global contexts including Islamic and Hindu fundamentalism.*

Keywords: *Revivalism, Secessionist, Appropriation, Public sphere, Hijam Irawat*

1. Introduction

Jurgen Habermas has conceived of 'public sphere' as "a realm of social life where people can bring up matters of general interest; where they can discuss and debate these issues without recourse to custom, dogma and force; and where they can resolve differences of opinion by rational argument" (Turner, 1987: 190).

An important proponent of Critical theory and pragmatism, Habermas' conception of public sphere (which he had refined as 'Communicative action'

theory later on), although sounds a bit farfetched in terms of real applicability, is the need of our time when right wing populism is on the verge of smothering more nations as the wheel of change burrows through time. And especially in the context of Manipur, the rise of revivalist tendencies has in a way given space for reclaiming the “lost” vestiges of an “ancient glory”, but it has, on account of the apparent overzealousness of some of the proponents and followers of this line of thinking, produced an environment of constriction whereby the need for a strictly scientific methodology to probe into history and the ensuing trajectory of contemporary fallout of the many unresolved “histories” is glossed over; rather, an overtly subjective and ideologically underpinned approach is vigorously promoted in the name of a complete overhaul of past injustices and miscarriages. In this process, serious and vibrant scholarly attempts to bring out alternative discourses and standpoints are crushed at the root, thus, resulting in self-censure of many scholars, established as well as upcoming, which eventually will only aggregate as collective loss in the long run, unless the scope for ‘public sphere’ is enlarged, and the treatment of historical narratives as sacrosanct and value-laden is snubbed. A resurrectionist endeavour that is based on flimsy and malicious constructions is unlikely to bear fruit, and rather would result in a self-defeating and reactionary *kamikaze* with absolutely no redemptive and emancipatory scope.

Paulo Freire writes:

“Sectarianism, fed by fanaticism, is always castrating... Radicalization, nourished by a critical spirit, is always creative. Sectarianism mythicizes and thereby alienates; radicalization criticizes and thereby liberates... sectarianism, because it is mythicizing and irrational, turns reality into a false (and therefore unchangeable) ‘reality’” (Freire, 1970/2017: 11).

He further writes that “not infrequently, revolutionaries themselves become reactionary by falling into sectarianism in the process of responding to the sectarianism of the Right” (*ibid*). Also, Freire says that “the sectarian of whatever persuasion, blinded by irrationality, does not (or cannot) perceive the dynamic of reality—or else misinterprets it and that should this person think with dialectically, it is with a ‘domesticated dialectic’” (*ibid*: 12).

Freire continues:

“Both types of sectarian [left as well as right] treating history in an equally proprietary fashion, end up without the people [or misguiding them]—which is another way of being against them...Whereas the rightist sectarian, closing himself in ‘his’ truth, does no more than fulfill [sic] a natural role, the leftist who becomes sectarian and rigid negates his or her very nature. Each, however, as he revolves about ‘his’ truth, feels threatened if that

truth is questioned. Thus, each considers anything that is not ‘his’ truth a lie. As the journalist Marcio Moreira Alves once told me, “They both suffer from an absence of doubt” (*ibid*: 13).

Freire succinctly and rather ominously, too close to reality for comfort *vis-à-vis* our own local context, describes the proliferation of “pseudo-nationalists and/revivalists” who are bereft of imagination as well as a sound historical training but who readily pick up chewed down “facts” and “rumours” (not actual narratives but dressed up thus) from obscure oral and fabricated written sources and then internalize them as truths to erect their “resistance”. The *modus operandi* involves negation/obfuscation of any well-established history if it doesn’t suit their pre-set “stories”, the suppression (often violent) of any critical countering that exposes their internal contradictions, and vigorous labelling and hyping up of the bits and pieces which reaffirm their confirmation bias.

Partha Chatterjee refers to lectures of Ranajit Guha who “discussed the conditions and limits of the agenda developed in the second half of the nineteenth century for ‘an Indian historiography of India’” (Guha 1988 cited in Chatterjee, 1993b: 76). It is analysed “as an agenda for self-representation, for setting out to claim for the nation a past that was not distorted by foreign interpreters” (*ibid*). Guha further points out the absolute unease felt by Bankimchandra [Chatterjee] in the nineteenth century Bengal when he declared: “We have no history! We must have a history!”; this exhortation in effect pointed at the need for “struggle for power [to represent oneself by recalling the past] ... the power to represent oneself [which] is nothing other than political power itself” (*ibid*). The point that Partha is getting at is the nationalist urge to reconstruct what is “true history” to them.

It is interesting to note that Partha Chatterjee in another work of his points out one of the distinct contradictions of the staunch nationalist Bankim who believed that “trade between India and Britain... had led to an expansion of agricultural activity in India” (Chatterjee, 1993b: 62).

Bankim’s predicament is that he accepts that

“The reasons for India’s subjection, and those for her backwardness, are to be found in her culture. He accepts that there exist historically demonstrated models embodying superior cultural values. His project is to initiate ‘progress’ by transforming the [currently] backward culture of his nation” (Chatterjee, 1986/1993a: 65).

Applied to the local context, the *Bankimization* of a sizable part of our population reflects and recreates the same compulsive, contradictory and irrational obsession with the need to “rectify” historical disequilibrium which

supposedly stemmed from some sort of an imposed *cultural Chernobyl* (key words being *mangthokpa*, *yanjinba*, *muthatpa*, *pusilakpa* indicating the admixture of spurious foreign elements); and so, according to them, without rectifying and resolving the religio-cultural issues and “reclaiming” a lost and sacred space, our current vortex of social problems won’t be solved. The problem comes when this ideological push spills over to the politics of the everyday and the private space. No wonder that the public space too is being gradually decimated to a dictated realm of revivalist assertions of the “lost glory” sort. Just like Bankim couldn’t, the revivalists haven’t resolved their own internal contradictions of defining what and sourcing from where the standards of social advancement they promise to deliver.

Clifford Geertz utilizes the interest and strain theories to understand the social determinants of ideology. “The former is a mask and a weapon meant to garner advantage while the latter, a symptom and remedy meant to correct socio-psychological disequilibrium. The two theories are not necessarily contradictory as they can operate at the same time too” (Geertz, 1973: 201). Further, Geertz writes that “the interest theory welded political speculation to political combat by pointing out that ideas are weapons and that an excellent way to institutionalize a particular view of reality—that of one’s group, class, or party—is to capture political power and enforce it” (*ibid*: 202).

Sutton et al define ideology as “a patterned reaction to the patterned strains of a social role... [which] provides a ‘symbolic outlet’ for emotional disturbances generated by social disequilibrium” (Sutton et al 1956 cited in *ibid*, 1973: 204).

The strain(s) are explained away cathartically. “Emotional tension is drained off by being displaced onto symbolic enemies (‘The Jews,’ ‘Big Business,’ ‘The Reds,’ and so forth) ... by providing legitimate objects of hostility (or, for that matter, of love), ideology may ease somewhat the pain of being a petty bureaucrat, a day laborer, or a small-town storekeeper is undeniable” (*ibid*: 205).

This is pertinent to understand our own situation whereby different groups of people are clamouring and rushing for cultural as well as religious ascendancy by resorting to the “othering” and “demonising” of the (constructed) rival group as the ultimate enemy. And the sweeping enforcement of generalisation one group devices over the (rival) other cripples any sense and space of empathy or resolution.

For example, the 2005 act of arson of the State Central Library by the group MEELAL demanding the replacement of Bengali script by the *Meitei/Meetei-mayek* script reportedly resulted in an irreparable loss of 145,000 books and manuscripts,

which is described by noted historian Gangmumei Kamei as “an incalculable loss” to our heritage (BBC report, 14 April 2005).

Carmen Brandt recounts a meeting with MEELAL members in their office in Imphal (March 2014) when “a board member proudly told me about their burning down of the state library. Convinced that the old manuscripts in the Meitei Mayek were destroyed by Garib Niwaz, MEELAL members seem to perceive the burning of the State Central Library as no more than retaliation” (Brandt, 2017: 23).

So, in an effort to “exact revenge” on a long dead historical figure for his blunders, the price is paid by the current unsuspecting generation. Garib Niwaz [or Pamheiba] here is the symbolic enemy that needs to be purged so that certain people can claim to have more responsibly taken up the role of “saving” the land that an 18th century king had purportedly damaged beyond redemption.

The problem is that historical evidences do not necessarily concur with this narrative of a destroyed and eliminated Meitei script— an important plank on which the revivalism movement is based upon which provides the emotional potency to move the very masses who need to be reminded of their “lost” originality.

It is a fact that the *Cheitharol Kumpapa* (the royal chronicle) is recorded in the archaic Meitei script [35-letter archaic script is used rather than the one of relatively recent origin, the official script containing 18 main characters, 27 characters in total]. Parratt and Parratt (2011: 21) note that the introduction of Western education led to the decline of the *Mayek* from the end of the 19th century and accordingly, it was confined to the *Maichous* (scribes).

Parratt (2005: 26) also observes that it was only after the Anglo-Manipuri war of 1891 that English education really became established, and debate around the language used in the primary schools followed. He posits that the use of the Bengali script for writing Manipuri, even though it is linguistically quite unsuitable, is explained by the fact that Bengali was used as a common language of instruction in the valley, and also since there was recruitment of Bengalis and Bengali-speaking Manipuris from Cachar as teachers.

Further, Somorjit (2014) bores through the myth of script destruction and the annihilation of important archaic texts (originally *korbek*, later on *puya*) by questioning why King Pamheiba did not destroy texts starting from the *Cheitharol Kumbaba* to *Numit Kappa* to *Chainarol* to *Ningthourol Lambuba* and several other books on genealogy. In fact, among the manuscripts that were written in *Meitei*

script under the authority of Pamheiba were *Samjok Ngamba*, *Takhel Ngamba*, *Charairomba Khunkum*, *Numit Kappa* (enlarged volume), etc.

To extend it further, he “even claims that the pre-Hindu religion did not rely on written sources, but on oral tradition, and that the burnt manuscripts must have been, rather, of Tantric content” (cited in Brandt, 2017: 11).

Brandt continues,

“The narrative of an abrupt elimination of the local religion and its related manuscripts seems to serve the construction of a ‘history of oppression’ and the strengthening of Meitei revivalist nationalism. The violent enforcement of a new religion and script is clearly more powerful for the cause of nationalism and revivalism than a slow, voluntary acceptance by the Meitei people themselves, i.e. a supposedly self-inflicted weakening of their own religion and culture. By commemorating these atrocities against the Meitei religion and script in a yearly public event referred to as ‘Puya Meithaba’ since 1979, the revivalists were, furthermore, able to spread this narrative among many Meiteis who otherwise often do not agree with the politics and violent actions of these activists” (*ibid*: 11-12).

As for the process of radicalisation elsewhere that in some ways parallels our local context, Sudhir Kakar, while writing about Islamic fundamentalism, says that “the indoctrination by preachers in some mosques and traditional Koranic schools begins with a lament for the lost glories of Islam... comparing the sorry plight of Muslims today with their earlier exalted status by illustrating with example such as that of Sultan Saladin [who while] commanding a force of thirteen thousand in the battle for Jerusalem faced Richard’s army of seven hundred thousand and killed three hundred Christians on a single day and so on. So, the focus is on ‘the weakening or loss of religious faith’” (Kakar, 2009: 132).

Kakar argues that there is a strain of despising the present as unacceptably dark and hopeless, whereas extoling the past and a hoped-for future as glorious and this is one of “the ideological underpinnings of the terrorist’s readiness to embrace death in carrying out his mission” (*ibid*: 133).

Sudhir and Katharina Kakar write, in the context of the Hindu Right, that “The Hindu nationalist, whether a member of the RSS, Bajrang Dal or the BJP, champions homogeneity and a singular identity... In his [paranoid] fear of a cultural alienation, especially through missionary religions and the onslaught of a cultural and economic globalization, he may be combative in spreading his ideology of a strong Hindu nation... The nationalist often seems split between a vigorous opposition to all foreign influences- proselytizing religions, cultural and economic globalization- which undermine the roots of Hindu *samaj* (society) and the tolerance ethic enjoined by the Hindu dharma. Hindu nationalism appears to be steering closer to the shores of militancy

than of tolerance, but the latter... continues to preclude an unambiguous commitment to the former” (Kakar and Kakar, 2007: 138-140).

Backgrounded by the above overtures, in Section 1, which have been utilized to understand the nature of fundamentalism, especially of the religious revivalism sort spilling over in the political narrative of nationalism in Manipur, this paper seeks to trace a concise yet coherent political journey of Hijam Irawat Singh, who arguably is the most charismatic and effective modern mass leader that the soil of Manipur has given birth to. By doing so, I would attempt to clear up, or rather counterpose the facts against the myths and appropriations that certain “adherents” of Irawat have successfully machinated. This is important because Irawat’s name cannot be uttered by separating the politics of the land, contemporary as well as historiographical. Also, the ethical aspect, of exorcising the unhealthy space and opening up of debate *vis-à-vis* the vested distortion of history and reduction of a legendary patriot to the caricature of today’s many half-formed political aspirations, is indicated.

Section 2 deals with the birth of Irawat as a social reformer and also his early political activism. Section 3 deals with his formal initiation as a Communist. Section 4 deals with the jail days of Irawat, his arrest in Silchar, the fissures and intrigues in the Mahasabha and the birth of the Manipur Praja Sangha. Section 5 deals with Irawat’s possible stand on merger with India. Section 6 deals briefly with Irawat’s underground phase and the late formation of Manipur unit of the Communist Party of India (CPI). Section 7 gives the concluding analysis.

2. Irawat as a Driver and Participant of the Manipuri Renaissance

In 1922, Irawat brought out *Meitei Chanu*, the first Manipuri vernacular journal as its editor (handwritten and lithographed) (Manihar, 2013: 229). Karam Manimohan in ‘Hijam Irabot Singh and Political Movements in Manipur’ writes that “Rajkumar Birchandrajit Singh, son of Jubaraj Tikendrajit Singh, bore most of the cost of the production and was its first publisher” (Manimohan 1989 cited in Sanajaoba, 2005: 40). He was also the first General Secretary of the Manipur Sahitya Parishad, and in that role, organised the first session of the Parishad on 18 September, 1935 (*ibid*: 54).

In 1930, Irawat and other theatre enthusiasts formed the Meitei Dramatic Union, which was later on rechristened as Manipur Dramatic Union (MDU) in 1937 to be more inclusive; the MDU is the first permanent and the oldest theatre to be established by the Manipuris exclusively (*ibid*: 60). His multifaceted artistic

prowess and natural talent for the pen is surprising in the light of the limited formal education he had acquired.

2.1. The Birth of the Social Reformer:

After having acquired the political and biographical knowledge of Lokmanya Tilak, Bhagat Singh, Khudiram [Bose], Netaji Subhas Chandra Bose, Mahatma Gandhi, etc. thus acquainting himself with how the freedom struggle was developing in the Indian national scene, Irawat started his career as a leader of Pan-Manipuri movement. He was elected as the president of the reception committee of the first session of the Nikhil Hindu Manipuri Mahasabha (NHMM hereafter) held in 1934 (*ibid*: 70-71). The major thrust of the session was the reunification of all the diasporic Manipuris based on “the pillars of education, religion and nationality” (*ibid*: 75).

The resolutions adopted dealt with issues such as— the need to extinguish the ill-feelings existing between the Meiteis and the Bisnuprias of Surma Valley; a Historical Society to be started for promoting research in Manipuri history and awards to be given to those who write the best historical accounts; the Manipuri language which is recognised by the Calcutta University be taken up as vernacular in their respective schools by the Manipuris domiciled outside Manipur; the old Manipuri script (*Meitei Mayek*) be popularised; a Provident Society be set up under the Government of India Act, 1912 (5th article); a committee be formed to check the immoral traffic in women and to bring back the Manipur *Baijees* (professional dancing and singing girls) to moral and decent mode of living; to promote and rediscover the ancient arts of *Thang-Ta* and *Mukna Kangjei* and for its implementation, competent teachers to be engaged in locality clubs and also competitions to be organised on the occasions of *Brabubahan Jayanti*; every Manipuri should provide their children with primary education compulsorily and that girls should be allowed to read in the boys’ school up to the primary stage; a Mission amenable to the Hindu *Shastras* be started to preach “Gourdharma”, etc. (Manimohan, 2006: 294-296).

Sanajaoba writes that:

“The objectives of the NHMM fulfilled the aspirations of the historical period but they could not transcend the boundary fixed by the feudal colonial set-up. The intellectual conception of the elite was also fettered by the suffocating ambience and the type of education in which they were nurtured. Irawat with his experience of the Swadeshi movement at Dhaka [during his student days] and his intellectual acumen could transcend the constraints in the perspective of his peers at the historical juncture” (2005: 87).

The Second session was held in January 1936 at Tarapur, Silchar with Irawat as the General Secretary and it was a spirited continuation of the First session. Some of the important resolutions adopted were:- representation to be made to the Railway and Shipping authorities for favour of employing Manipuris in the station lying near the Manipuri settlements in different districts of India and Burma; for the preservation of the individual Manipuri religion of the Manipuri emigrants in Burma, the Government of Burma to be moved for the inclusion of Sanskrit and Manipuri in the curriculum of the Educational Department and that relations be kept between the domiciled Manipuris in Burma and Manipuris of other places in matters of trade; if any Brahmin married a *Kshetriyani* after the Second sitting of the Mahasabha, he be made an outcast from the Brahmin society; a *Kshetriya* woman, if she be divorced and outcast after having been unlawfully married by a Brahmin, she be given again the same social *Kshetriya* status; the Assam Bengal Manipuri Society be established for the educational, economical and moral advancement of the Manipuri community for enlistment of all the Manipuris of Manipur and Burma, etc. (Manimohan, 2006: 297-298).

The Third session was held at Mandalay in February 1937 with Irawat as its Vice President. Some important resolutions that were adopted are: one M.E. School be established where Manipuri boys can learn Manipuri language in the town of Mandalay and local authorities be approached to help the institution; a *Manipuri Historical Research Society* be established in Burma in accordance with the 6th resolution of the first session; regarding the Hindu Manipuri ladies who have gone out of the pale of our society, by dropping the question of money in marriages, daughters be given in marriage to the bridegrooms of our own community in case they are deserving; a branch of the *Gouradharma Pracharni Sabha*, now a sub-branch of the NHMM be established in Burma; for the sake of convenience for the Hindu Manipuris living in Burma, the local government be approached to allot seats [to] the Hindu Manipuris in the posts of Municipal Commissioners and Honorary Magistrates of Mandalay town; with a view to preserving “Vaishnava Religion” of the Hindu Manipuris and keeping it intact, the Educational Authority of Manipur State be approached to include books on *Nityachar* and *Achar* among the textbooks in primary schools of Manipur and every Manipuri living outside be compulsorily made to study books on the above subjects, etc. (Manimohan, 2006: 300-301).

As reflected in the resolutions of the three sessions, the proceedings of the Mahasabha were steeped in the traditional, cultural and religious ethos under the shadow of the ruling Maharaja. But some progressive points also were exhorted dealing broadly in the areas of education (including girl child education), cultural resurgence based on *Sanatan Dharma*, economic growth and trading activities, morality, identity assertion including historical consciousness, much needed unification of the diasporic Manipuris, dispelling the rumour of incompatibility among Meiteis, rediscovery and promotion of lost arts such as *Thang-Ta* and other scientific and health-oriented ancient games and so on.

Meanwhile after the second session of the Mahasabha held at Silchar during 26-30 January 1936, the Maharaja and the British officers started to suspect that the Mahasabha would gradually assume the form of political organisation, which would surely tread on a path of conflict with the prevailing establishment. Maharaja Churachand and Angom Tomchouba Singh (Angom Ningthou) absented themselves from the Third session (Manimohan 1989 cited in Sanajaoba, 2005: 104).

After returning from Mandalay after the third session of the Mahasabha, Irawat launched a series of social reformation programmes under the banner of the NHMM which covered forced labour known as *Pothang*, forced sentry duty known as *yairek sentry*, *peon/amin chakthak*, i.e., forcing the villagers to provide compulsorily food and shelter to the peons and amins on tour in the villages, *Pacha Napet* and *Chandan Senkhai*, customary taxes levied on the Hindu subjects for shaving of the head for religious ceremony and applying the *chandan* mark on the forehead respectively (*ibid*: 117-118).

The fourth session of the NHMM marked a radical turn by taking a sharp political shape. It was held at Chinga in the last part of December 1938, with Irawat presiding as President of the session. The session condemned the repression carried out in Hyderabad, Rajkot, Mysore, Kolapur, Dhyankanol, Atgar and other Native States in Orissa, and sympathised with the heroes who sacrificed their lives in the struggle for freedom; and welcomed the news of introduction of responsible government in Mayurbanj and Jodhpur; expressed joy at the consolidation of the Congress Coalition Ministry in Assam under the leadership of Chief Minister Gopinath Bordoloi; expressed sorrow regarding the incarceration of Rani Gaidinliu in the Shillong Jail; adopted resolutions such as the Khadi Sangha to be established to revive the cottage industry and improve the economic condition; literacy campaign to be launched among the illiterates as the

rate of literacy being very low; the Indian government to be approached for keeping the hills under the State administration and reiterated that the hills–men and Meiteis have never been separated in language, in culture and in commerce; to demand for the establishment of a Legislative Council for the attainment of representative form of government for which an application has already been submitted to the Maharaja; the State authorities to be approached to abolish the practice of taking “Wakheisel” and to permit to appear in the Cheirap and the Panchayat courts with shoes and not to kneel down on the floor when giving statements; to request that Manipuri delegates be sent to the All India Kshetriya Conference; to request the Political Agent and the Assam Government to appoint competent Manipuris in higher grades in the Agency Court of Manipur; condoled the death of some of the Manipuri Muhammadans who died in the recent riot between the Burmese and the Muhammadans; to request the State Durbar to pass orders to make the State Courts and the other State offices use terms of civility in their summons and notices, etc. Besides the above, the Mahasabha, in an act of secularisation of its platform, deleted the word Hindu from its name to include all Manipuri. Thereon, it came to be known as the Nikhil Manipuri Mahasabha (NMM hereafter) (Manimohan, 2006: 302-305).

Irawat’s speech at the session, quoted below, marked the clarity of his political consciousness:

“Manipur is now under the administration of the State Durbar Members who were all appointed by the Maharaja out of his personal interest and matrimonial relations. These members were not selected by the public and hence, they would never think of happiness and prosperity for the common subjects. Elected members will only satisfy the people’s wishes and needs. I humbly appeal to all peasant brothers that these nominated high officers of Manipur will one day fall into your hands when their decorated legs of the chairs are suddenly broken” (Manimohan 1989 cited in Sanajaoba, 2005: 155).

Lokendra writes about the radical political turn of Irawat:

“The state government having realised the changing character of the Mahasabha tried to nip it in the bud. Soon after the Chinga session, the Raja distanced himself from its activities. The Government not only declared the Mahasabha as a political organisation but also issued an order on the 16th October, 1939 that all the Government servants should resign from the organisation. Many of the Mahasabha members subsequently tendered their resignation and many others withdrew from active work. In contrast to all these developments, Irawat Singh who was working as a member of Sadar Panchayat Court and Elangbam Tompok Singh, a clerk in the Revenue Department resigned from their respective jobs. The resignation... was indeed a turning point for Irawat because since then he started rigorous mass mobilisation programme... Reminiscent of *swadeshi*

days, Irawat [sic] burnt his and his wife's clothes in front of the *Cheirap* court¹. He further surrendered all the land grants and other feudal privileges enjoyed by him and his wife. Under his leadership, the Mahasabha submitted representations requesting the Raja to discuss the popular demands for constitutional changes in the state" (Lokendra, 1998: 133-134).

He started touring Dhaka, Burma, Assam, Tripura, Cachar and others, and to organise among the Meiteis and Meitei nationalities. It was in this context that, "during the initial phase of 1939 *Nupi Lan*, he was called out through telegram to lead the movement" (Ronel, 2017: 85).

2.3. Irawat and the Indian National Congress:

In the year 1939 Irawat had become an activist of the Indian National Congress. Before the outbreak of the Nupilal in December 1939, Irawat paid a visit to Silchar on 12 November and stayed there till 14 December, 1939 (Sanajaoba, 2005: 161).

Achintya Bhattacharya writes that Irawat's name "as the builder and leader of the State Peoples' Movement in Manipur... became familiar to us in 1939... [and in] the same year, Com. Irawat paid a visit to Silchar to assess... the Congress policy of those days.... Congressmen organised a reception for him..." (Bhattacharya 1999 cited in Sanajaoba, 1999: 1). He remembers Irawat as dressed in *khaddar* and donning a Gandhi cap, which was customary in those days (*ibid*).

2.4. Sedition charge

The part of Irawat's public speech which led to his arrest on 9th January, 1940 on the charge of sedition resulting in his incarceration for three years under IPC 124A is:

"Remember the Telegraph office incident. We begged for rice and in return received bayonet wounds and wounds from gun butts. For one handful of rice, we paid two handful of blood. Had we not paid this blood we should not have succeeded in closing the export of rice. The export of rice has been stopped and the mills closed at the cost of the blood of a *Brahmani*. Womenfolk have shed their blood for the sake of food and the menfolk should no longer remain silent through fear of arrest and going to jail. Be determined, it is not right to be afraid of jail walls. See what was the condition of Japan and Russia [?]. Rise and be united. The women's work is finished and now has come the

¹ Ronel (2017: 85) writes: "Everywhere in India, there were various forms of widespread movement to expel British from India. Irawat and his wife showed by example to the people of Manipur by following the trend of burning British cloths and wearing of *Khadi* (coarse hand-woven cloths) in other parts of India, by burning theirs in front of the *Cheirap* Court with the shouting of the slogan of 'Bande Mataram'."

time for the men. Let us take revenge for the spilt blood of the *Brahmani*” (Manipur State Durbar Criminal Case no. 4 of 1940 cited in Sanajaoba, 2005: 177).

Irawat’s fiery speech reaffirmed his single-minded conversion to an active political agent of change who wouldn’t back down compromisingly like many of his former NHMM colleagues who would in due course of time. It also reflected his logical succinctness and his awareness of international movements which he wanted his own people to emulate and internalise. By this, we can easily determine the broad-minded approach of Irawat, which was again a rarity in his environment. And the fact that Irawat exhorted and provoked the people in the name of a bloodied *Brahmani* reveals that, at that stage, he was still not purged of his *Vaishnavait*e conservatism, or probably he was using that line of attack for a more defined emotional impact on the masses. Although, it has to be said in his defence that his religious affiliation was not that of a regressive conservative but that of a progressive one, which has been proved without question by his leading activities against regressive and repressive practices of *Amang Asheng* (or *Mangba-Sengba*) and others.

3. The Jail Days and Initiation into Communism

Irawat was transferred to Sylhet Central Jail after serving one year during which he met many freedom fighters and he was exposed to the strains of the Gandhian and the Marxist-Leninist thought. As a result, his thinking and social outlook transformed (Sanajaoba, 2005: 194).

After his release from Sylhet jail, he continued to organise Kisan Sabha in Cachar under party command, and initiated movements calling for the abolition of *zamindari* tradition and for giving land to the tillers. He became the Secretary of the Cachar District Kisan Sabha and President of the Surma Valley Kisan Sabha (Ronel, 2017: 94).

He attended as a delegate of the Surma Valley Provincial Kisan Sabha to the Seventh Session of the All India Kisan Sabha (AIKS) held at Bhakna Kalan, Punjab from 2 – 4 April, 1943. However, he was not yet a formal member of the CPI (*ibid*: 96-97).

3.2. Manipur’s First Communist

Having been invited as a special invitee to the first Congress of the Communist Party held in Bombay from 23 May to 1 June, 1943, he applied for party membership. His application was duly accepted and thus, Irawat became the first Communist of Manipur (*ibid*: 98).

4.1. Arrest in Silchar

Irawat was arrested on 15th September, 1944 from a village in Cachar in the midst of his work as a Kisan Sabha organiser and detained as a Security Prisoner in the Silchar Jail vide Order No. C.141/42-V/210, Shillong, dated the 18th August, 1944 issued from the office of the Governor of Assam (*ibid*: 107).

Meanwhile, the detention order, dated the 10th January, 1945, was cancelled by another order, dated the 3rd February, 1945 with the condition that he should notify his day-to-day movements to the police (*ibid*: 117).

In the ensuing Assam Provincial Legislative election, Irawat campaigned along with Achintya Bhattacharya in a bicycle in January, 1946 and secured an astounding 13,357 votes against the much powerful Congress candidate's 17,430 votes from the Cachar seat (*ibid*: 138).

4.2. Political Intrigue of Opportunism by Irawat's Colleagues

At this juncture, back in Manipur, Irawat was clinically being sidelined by his NMM colleagues, who charged him of being a Communist. He was expelled from NMM unceremoniously (Sanajaoba, 2005: 245-46). He responded publicly to these accusations in several issues of the *Bhagyabati Patrika* demanding the withdrawal of the Communist allegations, and pointed out the necessity for all parties to work together at the then critical juncture (Parratt, 2005: 95).

Nonetheless, Irawat didn't stop his political activities. As per the 3rd resolution of the meeting of the Manipur Praja Sammelani dated 18 August, 1946, he initiated the formation of the Manipur Praja Sangha (urban-based organisation) after merging the Manipur Praja Sammelani and the Manipur Praja Mandal in a joint meeting of the Working Committees and workers held on 21 August, 1946 (Sanajaoba, 2005: 255-256). On the rural front also, he worked by strengthening the Manipur Krishak Sabha.

In the meantime, Irawat's well-meaning efforts to initiate the formation of a united political party was turned into hog wash by the calculating leaders of the Mahasabha who were well intent on grabbing all power and privilege in the wake of the forthcoming independence of India. Lokendra (1998: 196) notes how the increasingly insecure NMM leaders tried to delegitimise the growing popularity of the Praja Sangha and the Krishak Sabha by calling a joint conference on October 4, 1946 to discuss the possibility of a United Party; at the time of nomination of representatives from each political party, the President of the meeting refused to accept Irawat as a nominee of either the Manipur Praja Sangha or the Manipur Krishak Sabha. The Chairman of the conference also refused to accept his candidature resulting in the walking out of the representatives of the

Praja Sangha and the Krishak Sabha while the remaining members formed the Manipur State Congress.

The Nikhil Manipuri Mahasabha came into an end on this day (Sanajaoba, 2005: 261), thus marking a watershed moment in Manipur's modern political trajectory.

The political opportunism of the new elites/nouveau riche desperate to garner their share of power in the transformative crossroads of that historical juncture is clearly marked here, and their action of suppressing Irawat smacks of their insecurity faced against a far more charismatic and genuinely committed political maverick. In this toxic and degraded political environment, Irawat and his band of followers were the only saving grace in that particular socio-political context.

5.1. Irawat's Stand on Merger: Projections and Some Contradictions

A lot has been misconstrued regarding this point. A perusal of the public resolutions directly involving him during the period starting from 1946 onwards can dispel many untruths. Some important resolutions were adopted on 5 April, 1946 in the joint meeting of the Nikhil Manipuri Mahasabha and the Manipur Praja Mandal. Resolution no. 6 which was signed by Irawat as the Secretary of the Manipur Praja Mandal, and was forwarded to the Viceroy of India and the Governor of Assam on 11 April is reproduced as follows:

“(a) It is already a known fact that Manipur will also be included in the North Eastern Frontier Province which is going to be constructed according to the plan proposed by Prof. Coupland. This so-called North-Eastern Frontier Province will neither be included in India nor in Burma. This is a reduction of a part from Assam and a loss to India. It is a plan to prolong the suppression of Manipur and the hill districts which are dependent, undeveloped and are not yet given their due rights. This meeting strongly protests against this plan and the proposal as well.

(b) This meeting resolves that Manipur will remain as a FREE MANIPUR STATE inside FREE INDIA where the Manipuris will be able to freely develop their own educational, cultural, political and economic aspects freely. If those Manipuris residing in the neighbouring places of Manipur are willing to come inside the Free Manipur State enjoying equal rights, then their places will also be included inside the boundary of the Free Manipur State. And the people of Free Manipur State will decide by votes whether such a Free Manipur State will remain alone or will affiliate to any province of Free India” (Selected Documents of Jananeta Hijam Irawat, Vol. I, Manipur State Archives, Government of Manipur, Imphal, 1996: 72 cited in *ibid*: 249-250).

On 16 and 17 March 1947, the Manipur Praja Sangha held its third session at Khurai, in greater Imphal under the presidentship of Irawat. The session passed these resolutions:

“1. To provide one seat for Manipur in the Constituent Assembly of India by making appropriate arrangements for Tripura and Khasi State by reviewing the proposal for allocation of a single seat for Tripura, Khasi State and Manipur collectively.

2. To demand a Legislative Assembly and the abolition of the Constitution Making Committee in a common front with the [Manipur] State Congress.

3. To reduce the land revenue.

4. To provide civil liberties in Manipur.

5. To abolish the system of Inner Line Permit for the foreigners, etc.

(*Anouba Jug*, 1st issue, 13th April, 1947, cited in *ibid*: 270-271). (Emphasis added)

Resolution nos. 1, 2 and 5 are of special interest.

Again, in the *Anouba Jug* (the Manipur Praja Sangha and Manipur Krishak Sabha mouthpiece edited and published by Irawat) 19th issue of 12 August, 1947, the Manipur Praja Sangha issued a statement titled ‘May a New Life Begin from 15 August’. The statement which was signed by Irawat Singh, Bijoy Singh and Ibotombi Singh is reproduced as follows:

“15 August will be the beginning of a new era for Manipur also. It is felt by many that the day will be the beginning for bringing into existence a new government which has the closest relation with and is preferred by the people of Manipur. On this day all the organisations of Manipur will hoist the national flag of India. On the other hand, it is heard that the Maharaja of Manipur will hoist the flag of Manipur. This has caused the suspicion on the part of the people of Manipur whether Manipur would also proclaim independence like Hyderabad State and [whether] it would not be true that Manipur has joined the Indian Union as had been expected before. If this is true, then there is no rationale for the rejoicing of the Manipuri people. The people will not show its rejoicing, it is the rejoicing of the King only. The purpose of the gratification of the princes by the British is to leave a portion of India to the tyranny and oppression of the kings and it is virtually an aggression upon India. The people of both the British-India and princely states shall not compromise on this. We demand on this day of 15 August –

1. Manipur should join the Indian Union.

2. A democratic government should be established, a legislature elected by the people and a ministry elected by it should be formed.

3. Interim government should be formed by persons elected by the people.

4. The land revenue be reduced.

5. Vacant arable land should be made available to the cultivators.

6. Rural autonomous administration and the work of municipalities should be commenced within a short time.

7. The fee of school pupils should be reduced.

8. Compulsory primary education should be provided.

9. Inner Line Permit system should be scrapped” (*Anouba Jug* 19th issue, 12 August 1947 cited in *ibid*: 275-278). (Emphasis added)

Resolutions 1, 2, 3 and 9 are of special interest here.

In the 20th issue of 18 August, 1947 reportage of *Anouba Jug* is written that: “In Manipur the celebration of the Independence Day of India was begun on 14 August. In the morning of the day, *Prabhat Pheris* (people awakening others in the morning by singing hymns or national songs) were held and **the Indian national flag was hoisted in every local and branch committees of the Students’ Federation, the Manipur Praja Sangha, the Manipur Krishak Sabha, the Mahila Sammelani and the Meitei Marup.** All these organisations congregated in a large meeting at the Police Lane ground under the presidentship of Srijukta Irawat Singh. As the midnight of the 14 August passed away, the whole of Manipur was jubilant. The sky of Manipur reverberated with the slogans of “Bande Mataram”, “Swadhin Bharatki Jay”, “Jay Hind”, “Inqilab Jindabad”, etc. In the morning of 15 August, the volunteers of the political parties held *Prabhat Pheris* in their own offices and the national flag of India fluttered like waves in almost all the shops and houses of the town and in all the cinema and drama theatres. However, this flag was not seen flying in the offices of the state government (except the schools and colleges). The streets of Imphal town wore the scene of bubbling throngs of people. Meanwhile the Maharaja led a large procession from the palace to the *Kangla* and performed a puja there. The procession returned from the *Kangla* to the office of the Manipur State Council and the Maharaja hoisted the *Pakhangba* flag there. At about 9.30 a.m. Mr. Stewart, the Union Agent visited the royal palace and hoisted the *Pakhangba* flag at the Durbar Hall” (*Anouba Jug* 20th issue, 18 August 1947 cited in *ibid*: 275-278). (Emphasis added)

Interestingly, “the 19th issue of the *Anouba Jug*, dated 12th August, 1947, started with a big picture of the tri-colour Indian National Flag on the front page” (Ronel, 2017: 276).

6. The genesis of the underground phase

Ronel writes that “a protest meeting was called under the leadership of Irawat by Manipur Praja Sangha (MPS) and Manipur Krishak Sabha (MKS) at Manipur Dramatic Union (MDU) Hall at Imphal, on 21st September, 1948, against the proposed formation of a *Purbanchal Pradesh*” (2017: 207). But the Pundongbam incident (which resulted in the death of SI Naran Singh) changed everything.

As a consequence of this incident, the protest meeting organised at MDU Hall was adjourned and Irawat along with his associates had to conditionally go underground.

6.1. Late Formation of CPI Unit in Manipur; questions raised on it

Irawat “did not establish a full-fledged Communist Party in the state despite repeated instructions from the Assam Pradesh Organizing Committee of the Communist Party to do so long before... A District level organizing committee of Communist Party of India was formed on 23 August 1948 but the

full-fledged Communist Party [Manipur unit] came into being only on 29 October, 1948” (Sudhirkumar, 2011: 149).

It is relevant to note that

“The Polit Bureau, in a draft policy statement titled ‘Indian People’s Democratic Revolution and the Communist Party of India’, issued on 15 November 1950 gave the guidelines for advancing the armed struggle [which advocated] a correct political line... [to] further develop the present bases of armed resistance such as Telangana, Andhra, hill border regions of Mymensingh, Tripura and Manipur and boldly initiate the agrarian struggle and armed guerrilla warfare wherever possible” (Sanajaoba, 2005: 302).

So, why did Irawat form the Manipur DOC so late when the Assam POC had already repeatedly advised him? Answers could be gleaned from the Self-criticism he offered to the DOC:

“I did not know what criticism was really. Though I professed that criticism was a means to advance I was not convinced of it inwardly; so, I was afraid of introducing it in Manipur. I did not know that we should build up the organisation on the principle of the people. So, I did not build up the party because I thought that the people did not approve of it; I had no thorough understanding of the truth that the people should be made conscious enough to accept the party” (Sanajaoba, 2005: 299).

It is also to be noted here that “Irabot [sic] was sent to Burma under a resolution of the District Organizing Committee of the Communist party held at Kameng, Lam-lai-Basti, which was approved by the Central Committee of the Communist Party of India” (Joykumar 1985 cited in Sudhirkumar, 2011: 151).

Interestingly, the Central Committee of the CPI clarifies in May 1951 that the goal of Telengana struggle was not the overthrow of Nehru’s Government, the end of feudal exploitation (Sanajaoba 2005: 305-306). Accordingly, the armed struggle was disowned and the democratic path was adopted; preparations were made for the parliamentary elections which were to be held in January-February 1952. Correspondingly, in Manipur too, the Communist Party was formed in the over ground by Communist activists such as Thokchom Bira, Moirangthem Meghachandra, Soyam Chhatradhari, Nongmaithem Nripen and others (there came to be an underground faction too, running parallel to this overground faction). Thokchom Bira contested as a CPI candidate in the Parliamentary Constituency of Manipur in the first general election of 1952 (*ibid*).

7. Conclusion

Victor Turner cites D.T. Suzuki’s definition of *communitas* “as society experienced or seen as an unstructured or rudimentarily structured and relatively undifferentiated *comitatus*, community, or even communion of equal

individuals... [it is also] “a direct, immediate and total confrontation of human identities” (Turner, 1974/1987: 49).

So, the spirit of a certain well-defined/understood we-feeling of community is dwelt on here. Now, what happens when the spirit of *communitas* emanating from a mythicized figure in a particular society is questioned or disturbed? The Durkheimian conception of repressive sanctions might come into play as any such violation of the “sacred” spirit of *communitas* would probably count as violating the sentiments which are “universally approved of” by the members of that society— “the conscience collective, of beliefs and sentiments shared in common by the members of the society.” (Giddens, 2000: 75). But the more perplexing question is: who defines the spirit of *communitas* and what if, the spirit of its construction itself is flawed? If misconstrued in its foundation itself, then what price has the questioner to pay to expiate for having “disrupted” or “defiled” the spirit of *communitas*?

Victor Turner describes Miguel Hidalgo, the priest-turned-Mexican independence hero, who is celebrated as an inevitable part of nationhood and its social history, so much so that “he became not only the borrower and maker of myths but also a symbol himself” (Turner 1974/1987: 99).

In this narrative, “the symbol has swallowed up the man, and it is a symbol of *communitas*, of Mexico regarded in the mode of fellowship rather than structure” (*ibid*: 100).

The portrait of a mythicized Irawat as a secessionist

In the context of Manipur, a long-drawn history of lack of an immediately accessible contemporary hero-figure, a messiah, an indomitable and transcendental figure plagues the elite as well as the young minds. Add to it the situational role of Manipur being a self-perceived, correctly assessed David amongst the Goliaths of geopolitics and the continuing external suppressions regarding identity, space and the question of self-determination, it is then of no surprise that often historical figures are appropriated in politically tailored, misinformed ways. Irawat is one such important appropriated figure in the ensuing battle of narratives.

Thoudam (2016) cites M.S. Prabhakara who calls the claim of Irawat opposing the merger as “a strange reconstruction of historical imagination... [which is accentuated by him] being appropriated as an icon of the separatist armed struggles for Manipur’s independence.” As elucidated earlier in the paper,

the historical circumstances and available evidences have to be followed for a clear indication.

The conception of Irawat as a lone crack team fighting for total independence in the vision of a Manipur separate from India is problematic because:

a) The very political organisation (Communist Party of India) he was working in and leading till his last breath had its Central leadership in the Indian mainland. So, his actions and strategies were broadly tethered to the Central command. To adopt a direction radically different from the Central leadership would be scarcely thinkable considering how much of a devoted Party leader he was.

b) He was bound to the regional Assam Provincial Organising Committee (POC). And the POC was in turn bound to the Central Committee (CC) and Polit Bureau (PB) of the Communist Party of India. None of these organisational levels advocated secessionist stands.

c) His stand on merger with (rather, annexation by) India is not documented in black and white. The merger was formally completed on 15 October, 1949 and he was already underground after the Pungdongbam incident (of 21 September, 1948) till his death on 26 September, 1951 in Burma. In this long intervening period of almost two years between the official promulgation of merger and his death, he supposedly didn't raise any concrete voice against the merger as evidenced by lack of any communication mentioning the merger at either personal or organisational level. **He would have voiced dissent if he had the intention to and for which he had ample time.** Any claim otherwise doesn't find any supporting documentary evidence till now. But it cannot be denied that the surging Communist armed struggles which were simultaneously going on in Assam, Manipur, Bengal, Tripura, etc. were of anti-feudal in nature and not secessionist as such.

d) His participation in electoral politics (Assam provincial elections in 1946 and Manipur State Assembly elections in 1948) indicated his willingness to try through the constitutional set-up to bring about real and beneficial changes to the masses. He was an acute observer of the way politics and power mongering were taking shape among the coterie of local elites. That's why, when he realised that the process of instituting the Constitution making committee was corrupt, he demanded that direct elections be held for that. In the same way, he had raised the issue of the undemocratic formation of the Interim Government.

Interestingly, as mentioned earlier, the Manipur Praja Sangha in its third session, held on 16-17 March, 1947, had as its first resolution demanded that one seat be provided for Manipur in the Constituent Assembly of India and to review the proposal for allocation of a single seat for Tripura, Khasi State and Manipur collectively. This essentially meant that Irawat didn't oppose participating in the Constitution making process that was to be taken up by the Constituent Assembly of India. Further, if he had won in the Assam provincial elections and assumed the role of a legislator there, it would mean that he would have taken part in the indirect election of representatives to the Constituent Assembly, which was tasked with drafting the Indian Constitution. So, if Irawat was totally averse to the concept of seeing himself and his countrymen as Indians, then what is the logic behind participating in the provincial elections in the first place?

e) Irawat was not a narrow-minded regionalist. Partly due to his Communist background and partly because he was a humanist at heart, his approach was internationalism although his politics was rooted in Manipur first and foremost. This point is proved by how he successfully fought against the oppressive custom of dowry (*Panpratha*) that was prevalent in the Hindu Bengali society when he was in Cachar and also the Tebhaga movement that he actively led in Cachar. For him, the toiling masses of the Surma valley, or of Bengal or of Punjab were the same in the true spirit of a Communist emancipator.

f) He was dead against the re-entry of the exploitative Marwari class after the war, but then again, contradictorily, he pressed on to abolish the pass/foreigners' permit system. This point itself proves that he was open to trade and intermingling between his native land and the other far flung, more advanced parts of Indian mainland. **In which logical line would a hypothetically anti-merger person ask for the removal of pass system that could have an adverse demographic impact on the then small native state such as Manipur** [which anyway was haughtily removed by Mr Himmat Singh when Manipur became a Part-C state post-merger]?

g) One of the demands in a statement titled "May a New Life Begin from 15 August" signed by Irawat, Bijoy and Ibotombi of the Manipur Praja Sangha that was published in the 12th August, 1947 issue of *Anouba Jug* (Manipur Praja Sangha and Manipur Krishak Sabha mouthpiece edited by Irawat) is that "Manipur should join the Indian Union" besides the other demands pertaining to democratic reforms, land revenue, democratisation of Interim government, rural administration, etc. The same statement had condemned the "gratification" of the

princes (of the native/princely states) by the British, with an intention to leave a portion of India to the tyranny and oppression of the kings, as an **aggression upon India**. The gratification referred to here is the choice/right given by the Mountbatten Plan of 1947 to the princely states to either join the dominions of India or Pakistan or to remain independent after the partition of British India into India and Pakistan. The Praja Sangha statement's anxiety about the prolonging of the oppressive monarchy in princely states including Manipur even after India adopts democracy is understandable; but the particular part where the Praja Sangha describes the right given to the princely states to remain independent (and thus prolonging their monarchy rule) as an **aggression upon India** simply implies that **the Praja Sangha considers the independence of the princely states as harmful/antithetical to the idea of India, which basically means: don't break India**. This clearly doesn't imply an anti-merger stance and Irawat couldn't have been a blind signatory to the statement without understanding the implications inherent. And the 20th August, 1947 issue of *Anouba Jug* reports that the celebration of Independence Day of India in Manipur had begun on 14 August, and that **the Indian national flag was hoisted in every local and branch committees of the Students' Federation, the Manipur Praja Sangha, the Manipur Krishak Sabha and the Mahila Sammelani and the Meitei Marup**.

All these organisations had congregated in a large meeting at the Yaiskul Police Lane ground under the presidentship of Irawat himself. In the light of the above historical facts, the argument that Irawat was a secessionist is hard to defend. It is true that his political ideology had its genesis in his exposure to the dynamics of the Indian freedom struggle, and consolidated in his gravitation towards the Communist Party of India. And by virtue of that, he was involved in peasant movements and political activism beyond Manipur. What he learned outside Manipur, he tried to apply them in Manipur's own problems. Besides being a political leader, he was a mass leader in its true sense as he combined political activism with cultural activism. His well-remembered '*Thangol*' (Sickle) dance at the conference of the All India Kisan Sabha at Netrakona (Mymensingh in current Bangladesh) in 1945 was the highlight of his ability to sway the people with his charismatic talent that uniquely combined cultural performance in his political activism.

The very fact that despite being a well-fed Government employee (Sadar Panchayat member) and the king's close relative, he didn't hesitate in shunning

all those enviable privileges and relations when the occasion arose to take decisive steps to awaken the masses. This particular trait of sacrifice and altruism has been seen in the political players of the land since Irawat. Referred to as ‘*Comrade Ahan*’ by his underground followers, ‘*Big Tiger*’ by the State Police when he was on the run, conferred ‘*Kabiratna*’ by the Manipuri Sahitya Parishad in 1997 and ‘*Jananeta*’ by the toiling people of Barak Valley in 1959, Irawat cannot be reduced to a mono-dimensional figure who can be appropriated to serve whatever vested purposes for different interested parties. In spite of some of his political missteps, such as the late formation of the CPI Manipur unit despite repeated reminders from the Assam POC and his failure in properly disseminating the tenets of Marxism-Leninism among the Manipuri masses, he is still a tall figure who continues to give us scope for bettering our current situation by looking back at his methods and reapplying them after due adjustments.

On a final note, it has to be understood that Irawat was surrounded and befriended by opportunistic leeches who traded ideology and loyalty for the lust of political power, nevertheless he continued to work as a committed mass leader who could not be compromised. Things haven’t changed much since Irawat’s time as the same brand of opportunistic leeches continues to rule the roost in today’s political Manipur too. And many who scarcely deserve to even utter his name, let alone carry forward his uncompleted works, continue to appropriate him and his legend. His stand on merger has been twisted and turned around for a long time, and that needs to be put to an end for a proper historical closure. Further research by collating untouched documents and delving into unexplored parts of that period needs to be initiated.

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